

Technical Review API

Version: 0.1

Status: DRAFT

Author(s): Marcus Povey, Marcus Lowndes

The technical review API allows authorised user accounts (facility managers) to submit a technical review for a visit via the API.

To do this you use a mutation (`saveTechnicalEvaluation`) to submit the result of a technical review (positive or negative) and additionally pass a technical review field set.

Technical evaluation is performed by the facility for a given visit and tells ARIA, and the reviewers, whether the requested activity is technically feasible, e.g. in terms of the correct technology, or checking if whether the specific piece of equipment is available.

ARIA will only allow technical evaluation to be performed when a visit/proposal is in certain states, and this is dependent on the access route configuration (e.g. tech/sci or sci/tech). E.g. you will not be able to submit technical reviews for DRAFT, COMPLETED or CANCELLED proposals, or for ACCEPTED proposals where technical evaluation is expected before scientific evaluation.

You should check the visit and proposal status prior to submitting your reviews.

As a pre-requisite it is highly recommended you read the document "[ARIA Field Sets over API](#)".

Finding visits for your facility

In order to be able to submit a technical review, you must first find the visit identifier (VID) for that visit. Using a VID, as well as being able to submit a technical review, you will also be able to pull additional information about the visit and associated proposal via the ARIA API.

This information includes the full details of a visit, the full proposal object, associated deposited metadata, details about the visiting user, etc (assuming your account has the appropriate privileges of course).

There are several different ways you can find this VID:

From your Email

The simplest, but very manual, method of finding the VID is to simply use the VID that you received in your email when the visit was first confirmed to your facility.

For obvious reasons, this limits the amount of automation that is possible.

Webhook Ping

If your facility side management platform can have an internet visible management endpoint, it is possible to configure ARIA to "ping" this endpoint whenever a proposal is created or updated with a visit to your facility

Your endpoint will receive a JSON blob in the following format:

Name	Type	Comment
version	String ("1.0")	Version of webhook. Currently this will be 1.0, but will allow us to extend and change the format in future
event	String	The event, e.g. "visit.created"
context	JSON Object	JSON Blob describing the context dispatched with the event.
payload	JSON Object	JSON Blob containing the event specific payload

Where the context will contain:

Field	Type	Required	Comment
site_id	UUID	Yes	The site that this proposal has been submitted to
acid	int	Yes	Funding route for this visit
call_id	int	No	If access call then the associated call id
facility_id	int	yes	The centre this visit is for

And where the payload will contain:

Field	Type	Required	Comment
vid	int	yes	The visit id

You should respond to this ping with a HTTP 200 Ok error code. Please read the ["ARIA webhook specification"](#) for more details.

Query

Finally, you can use the visit query, i.e. visitItems to query for visits associated with your facility, however currently you will need to first find a list of the machines at this facility. This is a multi-step process.

In future, we intend to make this mechanism simpler, and it is for this reason we recommend the use of the webhook ping.

Get the access on my facility

Let's say you have a facility in ARIA, and you don't know how to see what access has been/currently been on it. These are some steps to help you do that.

Find the machines in my facility

First, search your machines based on the name of your facility to get the internal ARIA machine IDs of your machines.

```
query {
  machineItems (filters: {
    centre: "Biophysics Centre"
  }) {
    id
  }
}
```

Would return something like:

```
{
  "data": {
    "machineItems": [
      {
        "id": 8188
      },
      {
        "id": 5
      },
      {
        "id": 8190
      }
    ]
  }
}
```

Find the visits and proposals for my machines

Then, you need to get the visits and proposals on these machines. We currently don't support searching for visits by filtering on machines, so we will need to search for visits that have sessions on the machines. You can implement this by searching for all visits, while additionally pulling sessions so we can confirm the mid (machine IDs) linked to your visits.

```
query {
  visitItems {
    id
    plid
    status
    proposalItems {
      id
      title
      status
      submitted
      confirmed
      approved
    }
  }
}
```

```

    sessionItems {
      vsid
      mid
    }
  }
}

```

Would return something like:

```

{
  "data": {
    "visitItems": [
      {
        "id": 1,
        "plid": 6018,
        "status": "CANCELLED",
        "proposalItems": [
          {
            "id": 1,
            "title": "First proposal submission",
            "status": "REJECTED_BY_REVIEWER",
            "submitted": "2019-08-19 13:12:46",
            "confirmed": "2019-08-19 13:12:46",
            "approved": "2021-04-22 15:16:54"
          }
        ],
        "sessionItems": [
          {
            "vsid": 12,
            "mid": 4
          }
        ]
      },
      ...
    ]
  }
}

```

Where `plid` is the ID of the service on which the visit is taking place and `mid` is the ID of the machine, on which the visit's sessions are taking place.

You then will need to confirm that the `mid` for the sessions of these proposals match with the machine IDs you pulled before. In the future we plan to simplify this workflow by providing a single Type that can request all the visit data (`visitItems`) for a given facility name.

Finding your review fields

Now that you have your visit details, you need to find the field set for your query. Again, please refer to the document "[ARIA Field Sets over API](#)" for how field sets are handled in the API more generally.

Use the following query to extract your technical review fields, passing the access route associated with the visit.

```

query {
  access_technical_review_fieldsItems(filters: {
    access_id: 123
  }) {
    ref
    options
    title
    order
  }
}

```

Submitting your review

To submit your review you must use the mutation `saveTechnicalEvaluation()` passing the following parameters:

Name	Type	Comment
vid	int	The ID of the visit
tech_eval_positive	bool	true or false depending on the result of the review
data[]	array	An array field objects (see below)

As mentioned in the fieldset API documentation, data field will be an array of the following objects:

Field	Type	Comment
ref	string	The reference for this field
value	json	JSON-encoded value for this field

e.g.

```

saveTechnicalEvaluation(input: {
  vid: 123,
  data: [
    {
      ref: "foo",
      value: "bar"
    }
  ]
}) {
  vid
}

```

The field set will be submitted as the currently logged in user (as defined by the bearer token that is passed). Manage your accounts accordingly.

Version History

Version	Description
0.1	Initial draft